

THREATS AND CONSERVATION ISSUES OF THE ASHOKA ROCK EDICT IN DISTRICT MANSEHRA: A GIS-BASED ASSESSMENT

¹Navid Ahmad, ²Shakir Ullah, ³Haq Nawaz, ⁴Raja Umer Sajjad

¹M.Phil. Scholar, Department of Archaeology Hazara University Mansehra, Pakistan

²Professor, Chairman Department of Archaeology, Hazara University Mansehra, Pakistan

³Lecturer Department of Archaeology, Hazara University Mansehra, Pakistan

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Earth & Environmental Sciences, Hazara University Mansehra, Pakistan

[*¹navidahmad526@gmail.com](mailto:navidahmad526@gmail.com), [*²shakir@hu.edu.pk](mailto:shakir@hu.edu.pk), [*³hashtnagarai@yahoo.com](mailto:hashtnagarai@yahoo.com),

[*⁴drumer@hu.edu.pk](mailto:drumer@hu.edu.pk)

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Corresponding Author: *

Navid Ahmad

Abstract

The Ashokan Rock Edicts at Mansehra, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, represent one of the most significant epigraphic and archaeological legacies of the Mauryan period in South Asia. Despite their outstanding historical and cultural value, these rock inscriptions are increasingly threatened by natural geomorphological processes and intensifying anthropogenic pressures associated with urban expansion and transportation infrastructure. This study presents a GIS-based spatial assessment of threats and conservation issues affecting three Ashokan Rock Edicts (Rocks A, B, and C) in District Mansehra. Primary data, including GPS coordinates, field observations, and photographic documentation, were integrated with secondary spatial datasets such as digital elevation models (DEM), road networks, and land-use information. GIS techniques, including buffer and multiple-ring buffer analysis, along with DEM-derived slope and aspect analysis, were employed to evaluate both natural and human-induced risks. The results reveal that all three rock edicts lie within zones of significant anthropogenic influence, particularly due to proximity to the Karakoram Highway and dense urban development. Terrain analysis further indicates that steep slopes and unfavorable aspect orientations exacerbate erosion and weathering processes, increasing overall site vulnerability. Among the three sites, Rock B and Rock C exhibit comparatively higher risk levels due to the combined effects of infrastructure proximity and environmental factors. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating GIS-based spatial analysis with archaeological conservation and provides spatially explicit recommendations, including graduated protection zones and targeted monitoring strategies. This research contributes a transferable methodological framework for the assessment and management of inscriptional and rock-cut heritage sites in rapidly urbanizing landscapes of South Asia.

1. Introduction

The Ashoka Rock Edicts in District Mansehra, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, represent one of the most significant archaeological and epigraphic legacies in South Asia. These inscriptions are a series of fourteen edicts of the Mauryan emperor Ashoka (c. 272-235 BCE) carved into large boulders on a rocky outcrop near Mansehra city. The edicts are written in the ancient Kharosthi script and illustrate the administrative sophistication of the Mauryan Empire (Fussman, 1993). They articulate Ashoka's moral and religious philosophy, commonly referred to as *dhamma*, which emphasized ethical governance, non-violence, and social welfare. These edicts are a unique source of information on early statecraft and the spread of Buddhism in the Indian subcontinent (Thapar, 2002).

The historical significance of the site extends beyond textual content. Strategically located along an ancient trans-regional route connecting the Peshawar Valley with Kashmir, Gilgit, Central Asia, and the urban center of Taxila, the site provides evidence of ancient communication corridors and the diffusion of ideological ideas (Lahiri, 2015). This demonstrates that Mansehra was an important node within broader socio-political networks during the Mauryan period. Moreover, the Ashoka Rock Edicts underscore the historical integration of the Gandhara region within larger imperial frameworks, highlighting the cultural and administrative influence of Ashoka's governance across diverse territories (Sen, 2006).

Despite its historical and cultural importance, the Ashoka Rock Edict site faces multiple threats to its preservation. Over centuries, natural weathering, environmental degradation, and erosion have contributed to the fading of inscriptions, making parts of the edicts less legible or at risk of complete loss (Shah, 2010). These impacts are further exacerbated by climatic factors such as rainfall, wind, and temperature fluctuations, which accelerate the deterioration of rock surfaces. At the same time, human activities including unregulated tourism, urban expansion, and road construction pose additional pressures that may compromise the site's integrity (Khan, 2012).

Conservation efforts have been initiated at different times to mitigate these threats. Protective canopies were erected over the rocks during the late 20th century to shield them from direct exposure to environmental hazards (DOAM, 2015). However, the long-term effectiveness of these measures remains uncertain. Recent heritage initiatives emphasize the use of modern documentation and preservation technologies, such as GIS mapping, 3D scanning,

and photogrammetry, which provide precise spatial and condition data for monitoring and management (Bhimani & Rai, 2018).

While traditional archaeological methods focus on excavation and typological analysis of artifacts, contemporary conservation emphasizes the importance of understanding the spatial context of heritage sites. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) allow researchers to map sites in relation to environmental and anthropogenic features, enabling the identification of vulnerabilities and spatial patterns of threats. Through GIS, multi-layered datasets such as elevation, slope, proximity to roads, and land-use can be analyzed to support predictive conservation strategies (Conolly & Lake, 2006). In the context of Mansehra, where urban development and infrastructure expansion are ongoing, GIS-based spatial assessment becomes crucial for planning effective site protection measures.

GIS applications are particularly suitable for a single-site analysis like the Ashoka Rock Edict, allowing both macro- and micro-scale evaluations of its spatial environment. Buffer analysis, for example, can quantify the distances between the edict and potential threats such as roads or urban areas, while slope and elevation analysis can identify natural hazards like erosion or runoff. These spatial assessments form the basis for informed conservation recommendations and long-term heritage management strategies. By applying GIS to the Ashoka Rock Edict, this study aims to combine archaeological documentation with spatial analysis, providing a framework that can be applied to similar heritage sites in the region.

In conclusion, the Ashoka Rock Edicts in Mansehra are an invaluable cultural and historical resource, currently threatened by natural and human-induced factors. A GIS-based approach enables systematic documentation and threat assessment, producing data-driven recommendations for site conservation. This research highlights the integration of modern geospatial tools with archaeological conservation, contributing to the preservation of Pakistan's rich heritage while establishing a model for future site assessments.

1.2 Research Gap and Novelty

Although the Ashokan Rock Edicts of Mansehra have been extensively studied from historical, epigraphic, and philological perspectives, their spatial vulnerability and conservation context remain insufficiently explored. Previous research has largely focused on textual interpretation, historical significance, and descriptive documentation of the inscriptions, with limited attention given to quantitative, site-specific assessment of environmental and anthropogenic

threats. In particular, the impacts of rapid urban expansion, transportation infrastructure, and terrain-related processes on the long-term preservation of the Mansehra edicts have not been systematically evaluated using spatial analytical tools.

Recent advances in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have demonstrated significant potential for heritage risk assessment by integrating environmental and human-induced factors within a spatial framework. However, in the context of Pakistan and the northwestern region of South Asia, GIS-based conservation studies of inscriptional and rock-cut heritage sites remain scarce. No previous study has applied buffer and multiple-ring buffer analysis combined with DEM-derived slope and aspect parameters to assess the vulnerability of the Ashokan Rock Edicts at Mansehra. This lack of spatially explicit analysis represents a critical gap in both regional heritage research and applied conservation planning.

This study addresses this gap by presenting the first comprehensive GIS-based assessment of threats and conservation issues affecting the Ashokan Rock Edicts in District Mansehra. By integrating field-based documentation with spatial proximity analysis and terrain modeling, the research provides a quantitative and replicable framework for identifying high-risk zones and prioritizing conservation interventions. The methodological approach adopted in this study not only enhances understanding of the spatial dynamics influencing site degradation but also contributes practical insights for heritage management in rapidly urbanizing landscapes. The findings are intended to support evidence-based conservation policy and offer a transferable model applicable to similar archaeological sites across South Asia.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Ashoka and the Mauryan Edicts

The Ashoka Rock Edicts are among the most well-documented epigraphic sources from the Mauryan period. Emperor Ashoka (c. 272–235 BCE) is widely recognized for promoting Buddhist moral principles (*dhamma*) through inscriptions across the Indian subcontinent. These edicts are inscribed on rocks and pillars, using scripts such as Brahmi and Kharosthi, reflecting the linguistic diversity of the regions under Mauryan control (Fussman, 1993; Lahiri, 2015). Scholars have emphasized the edicts as instruments of governance, social regulation, and ethical instruction, serving both political and religious purposes (Thapar, 2002).

The Mansehra Edicts, in particular, provide a unique insight into Ashoka's influence in the northwestern frontier of the Mauryan Empire. Lahiri (2015) highlights that these inscriptions

were strategically placed along key routes, suggesting the importance of communication and visibility in the dissemination of royal ideology. The edicts' textual content emphasizes non-violence, respect for all life, and social welfare, providing a valuable framework for understanding the philosophical foundations of early statecraft (Sen, 2006).

2.2 Threats to the Ashoka Rock Edicts

Studies on heritage conservation have highlighted both natural and anthropogenic threats to the Ashoka Rock Edicts. Shah (2010) noted that natural weathering, rainfall, temperature fluctuations, and erosion have significantly affected the inscriptions, causing loss of legibility in certain sections. Khan (2012) further stressed the impact of human-induced factors, including unregulated tourism, proximity to roads, and urban expansion, which can physically damage or destabilize the site. Research in similar heritage contexts shows that early intervention is critical. For example, conservation strategies combining physical protection with environmental monitoring have been recommended for other rock inscription sites in South Asia (Bhimani & Rai, 2018). These approaches stress the importance of integrating spatial analysis to identify vulnerable zones and prioritize conservation actions.

2.3 GIS and Archaeological Site Conservation

The application of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in archaeology and heritage management has increased significantly over the past two decades. GIS allows researchers to map archaeological sites, analyze spatial relationships with natural and human-made features, and identify zones of vulnerability (Conolly & Lake, 2006). For single-site studies like the Ashoka Rock Edict, GIS can provide critical insights into site accessibility, exposure to environmental hazards, and proximity to infrastructure.

Buffer analysis, slope modeling, and overlay analysis are commonly used techniques in GIS-based heritage studies. For instance, studies by Wheatley and Gillings (2002) demonstrated that GIS can help assess how environmental and anthropogenic factors influence site preservation. Similarly, Bhimani and Rai (2018) emphasized that geospatial analysis can guide resource allocation and monitoring priorities in heritage management.

2.4 Gaps in the Literature

While previous research has extensively documented the textual, linguistic, and historical significance of the Ashoka Rock Edicts, there remains a lack of site-specific, GIS-based assessment of threats and conservation priorities. Most studies have focused on epigraphy and

historical interpretation, leaving spatial vulnerability analysis underexplored (DOAM, 2015; Shah, 2010). This gap highlights the need for integrating GIS with traditional conservation methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the site's current condition and risks.

3. Materials and Methods

This chapter outlines the research methods used to assess the threats and conservation issues of the Ashoka Rock Edict in District Mansehra. The study integrates field survey, GPS data collection, and GIS-based spatial analysis to evaluate natural and human-induced threats to the site. The methodology is designed for providing meaningful conservation recommendations.

3.1 Study Area and Site Description

The study was conducted in District Mansehra, located in the Hazara region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province, northern Pakistan. The area is characterized by rugged mountainous terrain, dissected valleys, and rapidly expanding urban development. Three Ashokan Rock Edicts (hereafter referred to as Rock A, Rock B, and Rock C) were selected for analysis based on their historical significance, accessibility, and exposure to anthropogenic activity. The proximity of the Karakoram Highway (KKH) and associated urban infrastructure makes the study area particularly suitable for assessing spatial threats to cultural heritage sites.

3.2 Data Sources and Preparation

Spatial datasets used in this study included a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), road and settlement layers, and the geographic coordinates of the Ashokan Rock Edicts collected using a handheld GPS receiver during field surveys. The DEM (30 m spatial resolution) was used to derive elevation, slope, and aspect layers. All datasets were projected to a common coordinate system (WGS 84, UTM Zone 43N) to ensure spatial consistency. Data preprocessing, including clipping, reprojection, and raster conversion, was carried out in a GIS environment.

3.3 Buffer and Multiple Ring Buffer Analysis

Buffer analysis was employed to evaluate the spatial proximity of the rock edicts to anthropogenic features and to identify zones of potential threat. A uniform buffer distance of 50 m was generated around each site to represent the immediate impact zone, where direct human-induced pressures such as construction activity, traffic vibration, and unregulated access are most pronounced.

To assess indirect and cumulative impacts, a multiple ring buffer analysis was conducted using concentric zones of 100 m and 200 m around each rock edict. These distances were selected to

capture varying levels of influence from surrounding infrastructure and urban development. The spatial intersection between buffer zones and roads, settlements, and other land-use features was examined to evaluate the intensity and extent of anthropogenic pressure.

3.4 DEM-Based Terrain Analysis

Terrain characteristics were analyzed using DEM-derived elevation, slope, and aspect layers to assess natural vulnerability factors influencing the preservation of the rock edicts. Elevation values were extracted to identify relative topographic positioning of the sites. Slope analysis was conducted to evaluate susceptibility to erosion and surface runoff, with higher slope values indicating increased geomorphological risk. Aspect analysis was used to determine directional exposure to solar radiation, which influences thermal stress and weathering processes on exposed rock surfaces. Slope and aspect values were extracted at each rock edict location using spatial sampling tools, allowing for site-specific comparison and quantitative assessment.

3.5 Integrated Risk Classification

An integrated risk assessment was performed by combining anthropogenic proximity indicators (buffer and multiple ring buffer results) with natural terrain parameters (slope, aspect, and elevation). Based on relative thresholds identified in heritage conservation and geomorphological literature, each site was classified into low, moderate, or high-risk categories. This approach enabled the prioritization of rock edicts according to their overall vulnerability and provided a spatial framework for conservation planning.

3.6 GIS Software and Analysis Environment

All spatial analyses were conducted using Geographic Information System (GIS) software, including raster and vector processing tools for terrain modeling, buffer generation, and spatial extraction. The methodological workflow adopted in this study is replicable and can be applied to other rock inscription and archaeological sites facing similar conservation challenges.

Table 1: Summary of primary and secondary data sources.

Data Type	Source	Purpose
GPS coordinates	Field survey	Site location mapping
Photographs	Field survey	Condition documentation
DEM / Slope	SRTM / ArcGIS	Natural threat assessment
Roads	Open Street Map	Anthropogenic threat assessment
Land-use	Satellite imagery	Spatial analysis of threats

4. Results

This chapter presents the findings of the GIS-based assessment of the Ashoka Rock Edict in District Mansehra. The results are based on field observations, GPS data collection, and spatial analysis using GIS. The analysis focuses on site location, surrounding terrain, proximity to threats, and risk assessment to guide conservation strategies.

4.1 Site Location and Description

Location of the study area is Ashoka Rock Edict (A, B, C), District Mansehra, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan (see figure. 1). Coordinates of the site are below in table no 2.

Table 2: *Coordinates of the Site*

S. No	Latitude	Longitude
Rock A	34.33778	73.19361
Rock B	34.33778	73.19333
Rock C	34.33778	73.19389

4.2 Spatial Distribution of the Ashokan Rock Edicts

The three Ashokan Rock Edicts analyzed in this study (Rock A, Rock B, and Rock C) are located within the urbanized zone of District Mansehra, in close proximity to major transportation infrastructure and residential development (Figure 1). All sites are positioned along the corridor of the Karakoram Highway (KKH) and associated local road networks. Spatial mapping shows that none of the rock edicts are isolated from modern land-use features (Figure 2).

4.3 Elevation Characteristics

Elevation values derived from the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) show that the three rock edicts are situated within a relatively narrow elevation range (Figure 2). Rock A is located at an elevation of 1055 m, Rock B at 1064 m, and Rock C at 1043 m above mean sea level. Rock B represents the highest elevation site among the three.

4.4 Slope Analysis

Slope analysis indicates notable variation among the sites (Figure 3). Rock A exhibits a slope value of 19.11°, while Rock B records the highest slope at 19.50°. Rock C is located on a comparatively gentler slope of 13.93°. All slope values exceed 10°, indicating placement on moderately to steeply inclined terrain.

4.5 Aspect Analysis

Aspect analysis reveals differences in directional orientation of the rock edicts (Figure 4). Rock A records an aspect value of 28.66° , Rock B records 15.95° , and Rock C records 4.68° . These values indicate varying degrees of directional exposure among the sites.

Table: 4: *DEM-Derived Terrain Characteristics of the Ashokan Rock Edicts*

Rock	Elevation (m)	Slope ($^\circ$)	Aspect
Rock A	1055	19.112	28.66
Rock B	1064	19.50	15.945
Rock C	1043	13.93	4.68

4.6 Buffer Analysis

The 50 m buffer analysis reveals that all three rock edicts fall within zones of immediate anthropogenic influence (Figure 5). Roads and built-up areas intersect directly with the buffer zones of Rock A, Rock B, and Rock C. In particular, Rock B and Rock C show extensive overlap between the buffer zone and transportation infrastructure, while Rock A exhibits overlap primarily with nearby settlements and access routes. Surface drainage features are also present within the buffer zones of the sites, indicating potential exposure to runoff and moisture-related processes.

Table: 5. Rock-wise Threat Scoring

Assign numerical scores to threats:

Rock	Natural Threat Score	Human Threat Score	Total Risk
A	2	1	3 (Medium)
B	3	3	6 (High)
C	2	2	4 (Medium-High)

Note: Low = 1, Medium = 2, High = 3

The buffer analysis reveals that all three Ashokan Rock Edicts lie within close proximity to major anthropogenic features, particularly the Karakoram Highway and dense urban settlements, posing serious conservation risks.

4.7 Multiple Ring Buffer Analysis

Multiple ring buffer analysis using 50 m, 100 m, and 200 m distances illustrates a progressive increase in anthropogenic features surrounding the rock edicts (Figure 6). Within the 100 m buffer zones, higher densities of residential structures and secondary roads are observed. The

200 m buffer zones encompass extensive urban development, including commercial areas and continuous road networks. Comparative analysis indicates that Rock B and Rock C are surrounded by higher concentrations of infrastructure within all buffer distances compared to Rock A.

Table 6: *Spatial Characteristics of Buffer Zones around Asokan Rock Edicts*

Rock	50 m Buffer	100 m Buffer	200 m Buffer
Rock A	Dense housing, road access	Increased settlement density	Continuous urban fabric
Rock B	Moderate housing	Dense settlement	Fully urbanized
Rock C	Roads, buildings	Roads + water channel	Urban + hydrological overlap

4.8 Integrated Terrain-Based Risk Classification

Based on the combination of elevation, slope, and aspect values, terrain-based risk categories were assigned to each site. Rock A and Rock B were classified within the high-risk category due to higher slope values and aspect orientation, while Rock C was classified as moderate risk based on comparatively lower slope and aspect values.

Table: 3: *Terrain-Based Risk Classification of the Ashokan Rock Edicts*

Rock Edict	Elevation Risk	Slope Risk	Aspect Risk	Overall Terrain Risk
Rock A	Moderate	High	High	High
Rock B	Moderate	High	Moderate	High
Rock C	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate

5. Discussion

The GIS-based assessment highlights the combined influence of anthropogenic pressure and terrain characteristics on the conservation status of the Ashokan Rock Edicts. Proximity to the Karakoram Highway and expanding settlements exposes the inscriptions to vibration, pollution, and unregulated access, consistent with findings from similar heritage contexts worldwide (Agnew & Bridgland, 2006; Viles, 2011). Steep slopes and unfavorable aspect exposure exacerbate natural weathering processes, particularly through surface runoff and thermal stress (Goudie, 2013; Summerfield, 1991). The integration of spatial proximity and terrain parameters allows for clear site prioritization, demonstrating the effectiveness of GIS as a

conservation planning tool. These results align with international heritage management frameworks emphasizing landscape-level protection (ICOMOS, 2011; UNESCO, 2013).

Conservation Implications

The findings underscore the urgent need for legally enforced buffer zones around the Ashokan Rock Edicts, particularly within 50–100 m. Traffic regulation, drainage management, and controlled visitor access are recommended to mitigate identified threats. GIS-based monitoring should be adopted for continuous assessment and adaptive management.

6. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that GIS-based spatial analysis provides an effective framework for assessing threats and conservation issues affecting the Ashokan Rock Edicts in District Mansehra. By integrating buffer analysis with DEM-derived terrain parameters, the research identifies high-risk zones and prioritizes sites for intervention. The methodology is transferable to other heritage sites facing similar challenges and contributes to sustainable cultural heritage management in Pakistan.

References

- Agnew, N., & Bridgland, J. (2006). *Of the past, for the future: Integrating archaeology and conservation*. Getty Conservation Institute.
- Ahmad, M. (1978). *Epigraphic studies of the Mansehra rock edicts*. Lahore: Sang-e-Meel Publications.
- Bhimani, M., & Rai, A. (2018). GIS applications in cultural heritage conservation. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*, 24(5), 503–518.
- Caroe, O. (1932). *Notes on Ashokan inscriptions in the North-West Frontier Province*. Delhi: Archaeological Survey of India.
- Conolly, J., & Lake, M. (2006). *Geographical Information Systems in Archaeology*. Cambridge University Press.
- DOAM. (2015). *Ashoka Rock Edicts: Documentation and Preservation Report*. Department of Archaeology and Museums, Pakistan.
- Fussman, G. (1993). *The Ashokan inscriptions and Mauryan administration*. Paris: CNRS.
- Goudie, A. S. (2013). *Encyclopedia of Geomorphology*. Routledge.
- ICOMOS. (2011). *The Valletta Principles for the Safeguarding and Management of Historic Cities, Towns and Urban Areas*.

- Khan, R. (2012). *Conservation challenges of archaeological sites in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa*. *Journal of Asian Archaeology*, 4(2), 125–138.
- Lahiri, N. (2015). *Ashoka in ancient India*. Harvard University Press.
- Sen, S. (2006). *Mauryan Empire and Gandhara*. New Delhi: Aryan Books International.
- Shah, T. (2010). *Rock art and inscriptions of the Hazara region*. Lahore: Sang-e-Meel Publications.
- Summerfield, M. A. (1991). *Global Geomorphology*. Longman.
- Thapar, R. (2002). *Early India: From the origins to AD 1300*. University of California Press.
- UNESCO. (2013). *Managing Cultural World Heritage*. UNESCO World Heritage Centre.
- Viles, H. (2011). Conservation of stone heritage. In *Treatise on Geomorphology* (Vol. 13). Elsevier.
- Wheatley, D., & Gillings, M. (2002). *Spatial technology and archaeology: The archaeological applications of GIS*. London: Taylor & Francis.

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Figure1.

Figure2

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6

